

LAKBAY-DIWA Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4389
p-ISSN 3082-575X

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4

VISIONARY VOICES

APRIL 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
INTERNATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4
**VISIONARY
VOICES**

Visionary Voices

A Global Visionary Discourse

Volume II, Issue IV (April 2026), International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4389 ISSN (Print) 3082-575X

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

Tracer Study of the Hospitality Management and Entrepreneurship Graduates

Dr. Teofilo O. Montallana

College of Hospitality Management and Entrepreneurship

Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines

Corresponding Email: teofilo_montallana@yahoo.com

Date received: April 22, 2026

Date revised: April 23, 2026

Date accepted: April 28, 2026

Originality: 93%

Grammarly Score: 100%

Similarity: 6%

Recommended Citation:

Montallana, T.O. (2026). Tracer Study of the Hospitality Management and Entrepreneurship Graduates. *In Visionary Voices* Volume 2 (Number 4, p. 40). Lakbay-Diwa Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19885486>

Abstract.

This study evaluated the career outcomes of Hospitality Management and Entrepreneurship graduates of Abuyog Community College from 2022 to 2025, including employability, the relevance of their knowledge and skills to their current occupation, and the challenges encountered in the job market. A survey questionnaire was used to gather data from 35 Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM) and 25 Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship (BSENTREP) graduates, totaling 60. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency counts and percentages). The respondents were given a modified CHED's survey questionnaire in a group chat through Facebook Messenger. Results showed that most respondents are employed, some working abroad; the knowledge and skills learned in college are relevant to their current occupation; they encounter high competition and limited job openings; and they have limited professional networks/connections. Based on the results of this study, the researcher highly recommends building partnerships with overseas employers and agencies to create internship and job placement pipelines, encouraging graduates to create their own ventures by offering incubation programs, seed funding opportunities, mentorship from industry experts, and integrating practical business plan development to prepare students for self-employment.

Keywords: Challenges Encountered, Employability, Entrepreneurship, Graduates Tracer Study, Hospitality Management, Job Market, Knowledge and Skills Relevance, Self-Employment